

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLECULAR WEIGHT, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC MOMENT, INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(II) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES^{a,b}

Complex/Stoichiometry	Found (Calcd.) %Co %N	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Λ_M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	$\nu(C-O)$ complex (ligand)	$\nu(C=N)$ complex (ligand)	μ_{eff} B.M. (Temp.) °K	ν_{max} (ϵ)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (sal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₂ Co ₂	18.2 (18.44) 4.0 (4.88)	642 (640)	8.9	1540 (1530)	1615 (1657)	4.70	8790(18), 18180(18), 22470(23), 8770(21), 18690(21), 22220(24)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-chlorosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Co ₂	16.5 (16.64) 3.7 (3.95)	715 (709)	7.3	1530 (1515)	1620 (1660)	5.04	8770(21), 18690(21), 22220(24)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-bromosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₂ Br ₂ Co ₂	14.6 (14.79) 3.2 (3.51)	788 (798)	9.3	1535 (1515)	1620 (1655)	5.30	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-nitrosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₄ Co ₂	16.1 (16.16) 7.9 (7.67)	735 (730)	3.4	1540 (1530)	1635 (1640)	5.08	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3-methoxysal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₁₀ N ₂ Co ₂	16.8 (16.86) 4.3 (4.00)	705 (700)	9.6	1530 (1515)	1615 (1640)	4.95	8800(20), 18520(20), 21740(20)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3-ethoxysal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ Co ₂	16.1 (16.21) 3.7 (3.85)	721 (728)	7.5	1540 (1530)	1625 (1660)	4.91	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3,5-dichlorosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Co ₂	15.0 (15.17) 3.3 (3.60)	775 (778)	5.5	1530 (1500)	1625 (1640)	4.92	8810(20), 18520(20), 22990(22)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (hydrox-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₂ Co ₂	15.6 (15.95) 3.5 (3.78)	754 (740)	3.9	1550 (1530)	1610 (1630)	5.24	

- (a) Abbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal=5-chlorosalicylaldehyde ; 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde ; 5-nitrosal=5-nitrosalicylaldehyde ; 3-methoxysal=3-methoxysalicylaldehyde ; 3-ethoxysal=3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde ; 3,5-dichlorosal=3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde ; hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and OHYBA=orthohydroxybenzylamine.
- (b) IR and electronic spectral bands are in cm⁻¹.

cobalt(II). The ir data, as discussed earlier, support this structure. The measured magnetic moments (Table 1) of the complexes are in the range 4.70-5.30 B.M. and are characteristic of magnetically dilute octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁹.

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Some Ligational Aspects of Tartrazine : Its Binary and Ternary Lanthanide Complexes

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 Manuscript received 20 February 1981, revised 19 October 1981,
 accepted 7 January 1982

TARTRAZINE is a basic azo-dye (Acid yellow CI 19140) used for dyeing food-stuffs and preservatives¹. It has also been used as a redox indicator² and as sodium salt in inks. It shows a yellow to purple colour change with pH, which may be used to explore the possibility of its being used as a metallochromic indicator. However, no attempt seems to have been made to study its complexes in solution.

The present work describes its binary complexes with La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺ and Gd³⁺ and ternary complexes with these metal ions using EDTA as a primary ligand.

Experimental

Standard solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates (Fluka, AG) and oxides in double distilled water and perchloric acid, respectively, and excess of the acid was evaporated. 1 M sodium perchlorate (Riedel) solution was used to maintain the ionic strength at 0.2M. The dye, obtained from I. C. I., India, was further purified by recrystallization. A 0.2 N NaOH (Sarabhai M)

NOTES

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ln-Trzne BINARY AND Ln-EDTA-Trzne TERNARY COMPLEXES AT 25° AND IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.2M(NaClO₄)

Trzne ⁻ + H ⁺	log K _n ^H	10.40		—			
Ln ³⁺	log K _{ML} [Ln-Trzne]	S _n	S _α	log K _{MAL} [Ln-EDTA-Trzne]	S _n	S _α	log K _{MAL} - log K _{ML} = Δlog K
La ³⁺	7.84	±0.02	±0.03	5.89	±0.02	±0.02	-1.45
Ca ²⁺	7.44	±0.03	±0.03	6.19	±0.02	±0.04	-1.25
Pr ³⁺	7.54	±0.02	±0.04	6.59	±0.04	±0.06	-0.95
Nd ³⁺	7.69	±0.05	±0.02	7.19	±0.02	±0.05	-0.50
Sm ³⁺	7.99	±0.05	±0.02	7.49	±0.07	±0.02	-0.50
Gd ³⁺	8.03	±0.05	±0.01	7.55	±0.05	±0.02	-0.48

solution was used to titrate the solution sets. The pH values were recorded on a digital pH meter, Elico model LI-120. The usual sets of solutions for binary and ternary complexes were titrated against the alkali solution and the pH values were recorded. The observed pH values were plotted against the volume of alkali solution (Figs. 1 and 2).

Results and Discussion

The values of proton-ligand stability constants (log K_n^H) and metal-ligand stability constants for 1:1 binary (log K_{ML}) and 1:1:1 ternary (log K_{MAL}) complexes, as computed by Irving-Rossotti⁸ technique with their Δ log K values have been tabulated in Table 1. The standard deviation and the limit of error have been calculated as S_n and S_α, respectively.

It is obvious from Fig. 1 that the ligand curve practically overlaps the acid curve in the lower pH region. Its separation starts after pH ≈ 8.00 indicating the deprotonation of the phenolic group of the pyrazole ring⁴. The separation of binary complex curve (curves A-E, Fig. 1) after pH ≈ 6.00 may be attributed to an early release of phenolic proton due to complexation. Only 1:1 complexes have been studied. The higher complexes could not be examined due to precipitation of the hydroxo-species.

The system under study for the ternary complexes is of the type MA + L ⇌ MAL as is clear from the pH-metric curves in Fig 2. The separation of curve MAL from MA occurs at a higher pH indicating the formation of the ternary complex, MAL, whereas the binary complex MA is formed at a much lower pH. Further, theoretical composite curve drawn by adding horizontal distances of the binary complex curves and free ligands, was found nonsuperimposable on the experimental ternary system curve. This confirmed the formation of the ternary complex.

The ternary complexes were found to be less stable than the corresponding binary ML complexes. This may be due to the coulombic repulsion between the binary complex (MA) and the incoming

Fig. 1. pH titration curves for binary Ln-Trzne complexes, A=La³⁺, B=Ce³⁺, C=Pr³⁺, D=Nd³⁺, E=Sm³⁺, a=acid curve, L=liquid curve.

ligand L, as shown by the following complexation equations :

EDTA being a hexadentate ligand, forms a very stable chelate occupying 6 coordination sites. Now, to accommodate a bidentate ligand, water molecules of 7th and 8th coordination sites of the lanthanides may be removed which leaves the geometry of primary complex undisturbed but creates an extra strain on the ternary complex thereby lowering its

Fig. 2. pH titration curves for the ternary complex La-EDTA-Trznc. a=acid curve, L=ligand curve, MA=binary complex (La-EDTA), MAL=ternary complex.

stability. This justifies the negative $\Delta \log K$ values in the present series.

In case of lanthanides, formation of ionic bonds is generally favoured, because overlap with the metal 4f orbitals is difficult due to the shielding effect of 5s and 5p electrons. This would mean that Born relation $E = Z^2/2r(1-1/D)$ should be valid for the complexation equilibrium under study. The stability constants $\log K_{ML}$ as well as $\log K_{MAL}$ being directly proportional to E , the energy change on complexation of the gaseous metal ion should yield linear plots with Z^2/r (Z is charge and r is radius of the metal ion). In the present case such plots (not shown here) show some deviation from a strict linear nature suggesting partial covalency⁶. Earlier work⁶⁻⁹ on lanthanide complexes support our observations.

The log-log plots of $\log K_{MAL}$ vs $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MA}$ have also been examined. The almost linear plots (not shown) indicate that the process of association of L with [Ln-EDTA] species in the ternary system is the same as the association of L or A with Ln^{3+} in corresponding binary systems. A slight variation is observed which may be due to the ligational nature and steric effect of the secondary ligand.

The $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MAL}$ values have been correlated with some fundamental properties of lanthanide metal ions, viz., 3rd ionisation potential, charge/size ratio and standard entropies. A linear correlation (not shown) indicates similarity in the nature of complexes. These observations are in agreement with the earlier work¹⁰⁻¹¹ on lanthanide complexes. The $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MAL}$ values have been found to follow the usual trend¹² with respect to the metal ions i.e. $La^{3+} < Ce^{3+} < Pr^{3+} < Nd^{3+} < Sm^{3+} < Gd^{3+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. V. Mahajani, Head, Department of Chemistry for laboratory facilities, and to I. C. I., India for a gift sample of the dye. One of the authors (S. N. L.) is thankful to the U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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Determination of Stability Constant of Copper(II) Complexes with Ethylenediamine and Acetyl Salicylate (Aspirinate) by Electrochemical Methods

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Manuscript received 9 October 1980, revised 16 October 1981,
accepted 10 December 1981

A number of studies on mixed ligand complex formation has appeared during the past decade¹⁻¹².

The present investigation deals with the study of mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) with ethylenediamine and aspirinate and evaluation of their formation constants by the method of Schaap